

Formulating learning outcomes: A quickstart guide

Learning outcomes describe the outcome of a learning process from the student's point of view, i.e. they describe the competencies that the student has acquired in the course of the learning process. Teachers can translate their teaching and learning objectives, such as the broad objective of "teaching the basics of thermodynamics," into learning outcomes by describing exactly what students will be able to do at the end of a successful learning process with respect to the content mentioned. For example, a learning outcome for the above topic might be: "At the end of the course, students will be able to explain the relationship between the laws of thermodynamics and various heat-power machines."

5 steps to a learning outcome

1. Indicate when the learning outcome will be achieved ("at the end of the course", "at the end of the unit", "at the end of the thematic block").
2. Specify who will have achieved the learning outcome ("the learners", "the participants").
3. Identify the content/subject matter to which the learning outcome relates.
4. Describe the acquired competence in terms of a concrete, observable action related to the content. It is helpful to use a learning objectives taxonomy such as that of Anderson/Krathwohl (2001) (see below) when formulating learning outcomes.
5. Define the type of action more precisely (inclusion of different aspects, observance of certain criteria, (non-)use of tools, etc.). This will make your learning outcome more concrete and easier to check.

Tips and tricks

- Avoid verbs such as "know", "understand," or "comprehend". Think about what observable actions students can perform when they have achieved the "know," "understand," or "comprehend" you mean, and describe these actions as learning outcomes.
- Use one verb per learning outcome and create an initial list. Then sequence and hierarchize the learning outcomes according to their location on the levels of the taxonomy. In this way, you will arrive at interlocking learning outcomes for individual units and can formulate the overarching learning outcomes for the entire course (recommended number: 3-6).
- Learning outcomes also describe exam performance in terms of constructive alignment (see above). Looking at examination tasks helps both in formulating learning outcomes and in selecting appropriate teaching and learning methods.

Example verbs for different taxonomy levels

complexity	Create (Erschaffen)	to design (entwerfen), to develop (entwickeln), to construct (konstruieren), to draft (entwerfen), to conceive (konzipieren), to generate (generieren), to organize (organisieren), to collect (sammeln), to write (schreiben), to combine (verbinden), to allocate (zuordnen), to assemble (zusammenstellen), to put together (zusammensetzen), to compose (verfassen), to combine (verbinden), to derive (ableiten), to prepare (präparieren)
	Evaluate (Beurteilen)	to check ((über-)prüfen), to judge (beurteilen), to assess (bewerten), to argue (argumentieren), to motivate (begründen), to decide (entscheiden), to evaluate (evaluieren), to classify (klassifizieren), to review (kritisieren), to estimate (schätzen), to support (unterstützen), to forecast (voraussagen), to choose (wählen), to value (werten)
	Analyze (Analysieren)	to differentiate (unterscheiden), to discriminate (unterscheiden), to organize (organisieren), to select (auswählen), to define (festlegen), to identify (identifizieren), to experiment (experimentieren), to contrast (gegenüberstellen), to isolate (isolieren), to segregate (absondern), to categorize (kategorisieren), to criticize (kritisieren), to sort (sortieren), to arrange (anordnen), to test (testen), to check (prüfen), to inspect (untersuchen), to compare (vergleichen)
	Apply (Anwenden)	to apply (anwenden), to use (verwenden/benutzen), to execute (ausführen), to implement (implementieren), to calculate (berechnen), to carry out (durchführen), to record (aufzeichnen), to solve (lösen), to plan (planen)
	Understand (Verstehen)	to explain (erklären), to illustrate (veranschaulichen), to summarize (zusammenfassen), to deduce (folgern), to derive (ableiten), to describe (beschreiben), to identify (bestimmen), to demonstrate (darstellen), to discuss (diskutieren), to interpret (interpretieren)
	Remember (Erinnern)	to recognize (erkennen), to indicate (angeben), to enumerate (aufzählen), to reproduce (wiedergeben), to name (benennen), to define (definieren), to report (berichten), to sketch (skizzieren), to allocate (zuordnen)

List of verbs compiled and supplemented on the basis of Ouden, Hendrik den, und Eva-Maria Rottlaender. 2017. *Hochschuldidaktik in der Praxis: Lehrveranstaltungen planen. Ein Workbook*. Opladen & Toronto: Barbara Budrich, 62-63 und Bachmann, Heinz. 2011. 'Formulieren von Lernergebnissen - learning outcomes'. In Bachmann, Heinz (ed.). *Kompetenzorientierte Hochschullehre. Die Notwendigkeit von Kohärenz zwischen Lernzielen, Prüfungsformen und Lehr-Lern-Methoden*. Bern: hep, 35-49.

Example learning outcome (in German) taken from Universität Innsbruck "Taxonomie von Lernzielen im kognitiven Bereich", <https://www.uibk.ac.at/bologna/curriculums-entwicklung/dokumente/taxonomie.pdf>, 7.